

Church of Saint John of the Collachium/Sencovan Mosque in Rhodes

also known as “Sencovan Camii”, “Church of the Knights of Saint John”, “Great Mosque of Rhodes”, “Church of Saint John of the Collachio”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Abrahamic, Greek, Aegean, Sunnism, Islam, Christian, Language, Turkic, Religious Place

The building was originally a three-aisled church dedicated to St. John the Baptist. It was built by the Knights of St. John ca. 1310 after their conquest of Rhodes, which had previously been under the control of the Byzantine emperor Andronikos II Palaiologos. As the main church of the Knights of St. John, the church was the site of worship, but also of the legislative meetings of the Order and the election of the Order's Grand Master. After the Ottoman conquest of Rhodes in 1522, the building was converted into the Sencovan Mosque (an Ottomanized version of the name St. John), and was also referred to as the Grand Mosque of Rhodes. According to Evliya Celebi, an Ottoman traveller writing in ca. 1671, the Knights of St. John had placed the body of St. John next to the altar of the church, and had taken the body with them when they departed the island in 1522. This account appears to refer to the relic of St. John the Baptist, consisting of the right hand and arm, that was most likely given by Sultan Bayezid II to the knight as a diplomatic gift in 1484 (although it is possible that the relic, or an earlier version of dubious authenticity, had already reached the island by 1413). The relic was the object of pilgrimage for medieval travelers, including Luchino da Campo in 1413, Hans Rot and Girnand von Schwalbach in 1440. In 1863, Sencovan Mosque was destroyed after lightning hit the gunpowder stored in its bell tower. The Church of the Annunciation near Mandraki Harbor in Rhodes, built in the 1920s under Italian rule, was modeled after the destroyed Church of Saint John of the Collachium.

Date Range: 1310 CE - 1863 CE

Region: Sencovan Mosque in Rhodes

Region tags: Greece, Aegean

Approximate area of the Sencovan Mosque, earlier the Church of St. John, in Rhodes (now destroyed).

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Evliya. Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi. Translated by Seyit Ali Kahraman. Vol. 9/1. Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2010.

– Source 2: Evliya. Evliya Çelebi, *Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi*, Vol. IX. Translated by Yücel Dağlı, Seyit Ali Kahraman, and Robert Dankoff, 2005.

Notes: Source 1 is the translation of Evliya Celebi's travelogue into modern Turkish; Source 2 is the transliteration of Evliya Celebi's travelogue from Ottoman Turkish into the Latin alphabet. Unless otherwise noted, references within this database entry refer to the modern Turkish translation (Source 1).

– Source 1: Zoitou, Sofia. "Chapter 1: The Hospitallers' Institutions." In *Staging Holiness: The Case of Hospitaller Rhodes*, 13–139. *Mediterranean Art Histories*, Vol. 3. Brill, 2021.

– Source 1: Dellas, Giorgios. "Süleyman Mosque." In *Ottoman Architecture in Greece*, 360–63. Hellenic Ministry of Culture, 2008.

Notes: Note that Süleyman Mosque is a separate, nearby structure in the Old Town of Rhodes, but is not the same building as Sencovan Mosque.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://ecotourism-greece.com/attractions/the-church-of-st-john-of-the-collachium/>

– Source 1 Description: A brief description of the church ruins.

– Source 1 URL: <https://brill.com/display/book/9789004444225/BP000009.xml?language=en>

– Source 1 Description: Online version of "St. John of the Collachium," a chapter by Sofia Zoitou.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Italian excavations were carried out by Pietro Lojacono in 1932 and 1934. In 1989, the Ephorate of Byzantine Antiquities conducted excavations.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1932, 1934, 1989

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Italian excavation, directed by Pietro Lojacono

Notes: 1932 and 1934

– Official or descriptive name: Excavation of the 4th Ephorate of Byzantine Antiquities

Notes: 1989

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

- ↳ Type of elevation
 - Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

- ↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:
 - No

- ↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
 - Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A single structure
 - Yes

- ↳ The structure has a definite shape
 - Rectangular
- ↳ One single feature
 - Other [specify]: N/A
- ↳ A group of structures:
 - No
- ↳ A group of features:
 - No
- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - No
- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
 - Worship
 - ↳ Worship:
 - Communal
- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - Yes
 - ↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
 - Collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Human-caused accident

Notes: Gunpowder, stored in the bell tower, was struck by lightning.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: While the structure itself is in a ruined state, the Church of the Annunciation, built by Mandraki Harbor in Rhodes, was intended as a replica of the Church of St. John/Sencovan Mosque.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

–Yes [specify]: Trinity

Notes: This church was used for worship of the Holy Trinity, and was dedicated to St. John the Baptist.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1310 CE - 1522 CE

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

–Yes [specify]: Trinity, St. John

Notes: As a church, this building was dedicated to the worship of the Holy Trinity; it was also dedicated to St. John the Baptist.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1310 CE - 1522 CE

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1522 CE - 1863 CE

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

–Yes [specify]: Monotheistic God (Allah)

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Notes: Christ was viewed as both fully divine and fully human; St. John, to whom this church was dedicated, was not regarded as divine.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1310 CE - 1522 CE

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: The church was dedicated to St. John the Baptist.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1310 CE - 1522 CE

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

– No

Notes: As an Ottoman mosque, this church was not used for veneration or worship of non-divine ancestors.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

Notes: Knights of St. John

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Notes: Conquest of Rhodes by the Knights of St. John.

↳ Specify

– War/battle

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1310 CE - 1522 CE

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– No

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:
– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract
– Yes

↳ Floral motifs
– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy
– No

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:
– No

↳ Are there statues present:
– Yes

↳ Cult statues:
– No

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:
– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Tapestries.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1310 CE - 1522 CE

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - Yes
- ↳ Humans
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - No
- ↳ Human narratives
 - No
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: N/A.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

– Yes

Notes: Relics of St. John, specifically the right arm and hand, were housed within the church.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1522 CE - 1863 CE

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1310 CE - 1522 CE

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

Notes: St. John the Baptist was venerated.

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– Yes

Notes: The place was used for the worship of Christ.

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Yes

Notes: St. John the Baptist was venerated.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1310 CE - 1522 CE

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:
Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity
– No

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: Individual burials

Notes: Prominent members of the Order of St. John were also buried here.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:
– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– Yes

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– Yes

- ↳ Are they other:
 - Other [specify]: N/A.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - No

- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - No

- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No

- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No

- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Through answered prayer

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Angels and/or djinn.

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Notes: Although Christ was considered to be present in the Eucharist, Catholic doctrine taught that he was both fully human and fully divine, and that these two natures were not mixed.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1310 CE - 1522 CE

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1522 CE - 1863 CE

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Notes: Although it is likely that there was a 'cult statue' such as a crucifix, the high god was not considered to be present within the cult statue, and was instead present in the Eucharist.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Communication to God was done through prayer.

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
– specify: 50-300

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: Daily

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– Yes
Notes: Wine was consumed as part of the Eucharist.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:
– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:
– No

↳ Are there human sacrifices:
– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:
– Yes [specify]: Sacrifice of Christ
Notes: The eucharist was associated with the death of Christ.

Are there self-sacrifices present:
– Yes

↳ Suicide

– No

↳ Bloodletting

– Yes

↳ Mutilation

– Yes

↳ Is self-sacrifice common and/or expect of elites:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– No

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: Men

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrims came to the church to see the relics of St. John, as well as other relics reportedly made from the True Cross.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1310 CE - 1522 CE

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Annual

Notes: Each festival celebrated at this place was celebrated once per year; under the Knights of St. John, the Feast of the Purification of the Blessed Virgin, the Ascension, the Nativity of St. John the Baptist, and the Assumption were particularly emphasized (Zoitou 16).

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1310 CE - 1522 CE

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: During the Ottoman period, all Muslim members of society took part in the festivals; Jewish and Christian members of society were permitted their own religious observations.

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: 50-300

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Non-elites

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1310 CE - 1522 CE

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: Under the Knights of St. John, the members of the order retained their ethnic affiliations through the division of the Order into seven tongues: Auvergne, France, Provence, Aragon, Italy, Germany and England. In 1462, Aragon was split into Aragon and Castille, making for a total of 8 units.

– No

Notes: Under the Ottomans, religious specialists were not of a specific ethnicity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1522 CE - 1863 CE

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: The mosque of Sencovan was supported by a vakf.

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

Notes: Elections within the Order were held here.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1310 CE - 1522 CE

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

- ↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:
 - No
- ↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:
 - No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Church of Saint John of the Collachium/Sencovan Mosque in Rhodes, Zoitou, Sofia. "Chapter 1: The Hospitallers' Institutions". In *Staging Holiness: The Case of Hospitaller Rhodes*, 13-139. *Mediterranean Art Histories*, Vol. 3. Brill, 2021.

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Reference: Church of Saint John of the Collachium/Sencovan Mosque in Rhodes, Evliya. *Evliya Çelebi, Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi*, Vol. IX. Translated by Yücel Dağlı, Seyit Ali Kahraman, and Robert Dankoff, 2005.

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